

8th International Conference on

Euro Pediatrics Week

February 25-26, 2019
Zurich, Switzerland

Theme: Excellence in Pediatrics and Neonatal Research

Invitation

Welcome to Zurich, the City of Arts and Science, and experience the science of 8th International Conference on Euro Pediatrics Week illuminated as never before. EuroSciCon is proud to host the Pediatrics Week and Regulatory Measures, February 25-26, 2019 in Zurich, Switzerland. This year's theme is Global Forum of Innovations in Pediatrics Week . Pediatrics Week 2019 will provide an unprecedented opportunity for scientists and researchers of all stripes and colors to share their research with colleagues, and discuss and debate the latest advances in the field. We invite Scientists, Researchers, and entrepreneurs in related disciplines to come together and inform each other in an environment conducive to education and interaction. Seasoned scientists, young researchers, mid-career professionals and just starting out are all welcome.

With a broad array of keynote presentations, panel discussions, workshops, and poster sessions, the Pediatrics Week 2019 Conference is the perfect venue not only to dive into your particular research interests but also to expand the scope of your knowledge. Tracks are devoted to very upcoming and challenging parts of Pediatrics.

The Organizing Committee has done its best to set up a framework that we think will allow for a creative interplay of ideas. All we need now to convert the extensive program on paper to an active and vibrant research forum in person is your active participation.

A Transformational Learning Experience

- Curated to address the concerns of today's scientific world
- Be inspired by some of the world's most renowned figures
- Stimulate new ways of thinking and provoke action.
- Relish inspiring interaction between peers, leaving you better prepared to face technical and research oriented challenges.

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Why with us?

We at EuroSciCon strive to create transforming experiences, propelling researchers and organizations to interact and come up with actionable ideas thus enhancing the quality of research and development.

And here's why you associate with us

Our International Open Access Journals:

We embrace around 700+ Leading-edge Peer Reviewed Open Access Journals and a 21 Day Rapid Review Process with a whopping 50000+ Editorial Board Team, 35000+ Reviewers team and 1000+ Scientific Associations Collaborations.

Read by over 30 Million Patrons and 100000+ Facebook Likes comprehending the High online presence, our Open Access Journals serve the best blend of content and global exposure.

Our International Scientific Conferences:

With over 3000 Conferences happening across the globe in the streams of Medical, Pharma, Engineering, Science, Technology and Business our events are accredited with CPD.

Moreover you get to meet the industry's high priests who come from all over the orb. You learn from the companies defined by their progressive ethos and dynamic strategies and also through the highly interactive sessions and panel discussions.

B2B Meetings with enriching interaction help building better businesses, people and world.

Other salient features comprehend:

Publishing of the accepted abstracts in our inordinately indexed journals

Each of which will be labelled with a Digital Object Identification Number (DOI) provided by Cross Ref Distinct abstract and Speaker page creation, which profusely aid in citing the research and researcher in the top search engines.

Career Guidance Workshops for students and early career researchers

Opportunity to publish full Manuscripts in our Open Access Journals

With over 25000+ pediatric scientists accessing the website, Pediatrics Week 2019 is the most lucrative platform for researchers, academicians and industry professionals pursuing their work in the field and related. In addition to immense networking opportunities, global prominence of the research and the researcher is what we bestow our Speakers and Committee Members fuelling better outreach of the work and profile.

Pediatrics Week 2019 Salient Features:

In a world of information overload, we focus on the issues most relevant to today's technical trends enabling our patrons to

- Congregate with most senior executives*
- Nurture connexions*
- Agenda format which incorporates ample Q&A time*
- Partake in our revamped exhibitor expo sessions*
- Meet and listen to the relevant clients*
- Unprecedented growth creating an unparalleled market place*

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How's EuroSciCon different?

- Exercises your creative instincts with the live knowledge experience*
- It organizes 3000+ Conferences across the globe connecting different sciences in 30+ countries*
- Over 25 Million+ Visitors and 20000+ Unique Visitors per conference*
- World's leading industries and companies attend*
- Career guidance for early career researchers and students*
- Provides insights you need to take your research to the next level*
- A huge conclave of high tech and science priests*

Who'd be attending?

The Conference on 8th International Conference on Euro Pediatrics Week plays host for the Multinational organizations, entrepreneurs across the globe, the researchers and academicians. Prominently Pediatrics Consultants, Neonatal Specialists, Pediatric Professionals, Laboratory Directors and Chemists, Neonatal Scientists and Researches and others who stay plunged in learning and practice in the filed of Pediatrics

About hosting organization

EuroSciCon is one among Europe's largest and most significant scientific place which serves as a crossroad for the academicians and industry experts to build networks. With over 16 years of Life Science Communication it focuses on to Spearheading the Transformation of Medical Research into Knowledge through Scientific Gatherings and Networking. Supporting the Rare Care UK organization, EuroSciCon is a corporate member of Royal Society of Biology, Institute of Biomedical Science (IBMS) and British Society for Immunology. Our approach has always been unique, and that difference has propelled our growth towards Scientific Serendipity.

Scientific Sessions:

- Pediatrics
- General and Clinical Pediatrics
- Neonatology and Perinatology
- Autism/ ADHD/ Anxiety
- Pediatric Immunology and Infectious Diseases
- Preterm-birth Complications and Neonatal Intensive Care
- Child Nutrition and Development
- Pediatric Allergy and Respiratory Disorders
- Neonatal and Primary Care
- Breast Feeding
- Pediatric Nursing
- Pediatric Cardiology & Hematology
- Pediatric Mental Health and Psychology
- Child and Adolescent Obesity
- Pediatric Surgery
- Pediatric Genetic Disorders
- Pediatrics Critical Care and Emergency Medicine
- Child abuse and Prevention
- Pediatric Rehabilitation
- Pediatric Vaccines and Immunization
- Pediatric Gastroenterology and Hepatology
- Pediatric Endocrinology & Diabetes
- Pediatric Pulmonology & Sleep Medicine
- Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology
- Pediatric Dermatology
- Pediatric Hospice and Palliative Care
- Pediatric Oncology & Radiology

See your work PUBLISHED in one of our related journals

- Pediatrics & Therapeutics
- Journal of Pediatrics & Therapeutics
- Current Pediatric Research

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About Destination Zurich

Zurich is the largest city in Switzerland and the capital of the canton of Zurich. Zurich was founded by the Romans, who in 15 BC called it Turicum. It is located in north-central Switzerland at the north-western tip of Lake Zurich. The official language of Zurich is German but the main spoken language is the local variant of the Alemannic Swiss German dialect. Zurich is a hub for railways, roads, and air traffic. Both Zürich Airport and railway station are the largest and busiest in the country.

Zurich is a leading global city and among the world's largest financial centers despite having a relatively small population. The city is home to a large number of financial institutions and banking giants. Most of Switzerland's research and development centers are concentrated in Zurich and the low tax rates attract overseas companies to set up their headquarters there.

Many museums and art galleries can be found in the city, including the Swiss National Museum and the Kunsthaus. Schauspielhaus Zurich is one of the most important theatres in the German-speaking world.

Monocle's 2012 "Quality of Life Survey" ranked Zurich first on a list of the top 25 cities in the world "to make a base within". According to several surveys from 2006 to 2008, Zurich was named the city with the best quality of life in the world as well as the wealthiest city in Europe. The Economist Intelligence Unit's Global Liveability Ranking sees Zurich rank among the top ten most loveable cities in the world.

Venue and Accommodation

Zurich, Switzerland

Register Now!

**Want to be a Part of the Leading
Pediatrics Week Event in 2019?**

Choose your Category:

Academic \$399

Business \$649

Delegate \$499

Student \$249

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Package Registrations

Academic: Package A: \$799

Package B: \$999

Business: Package A: \$899

Package B: \$1099

HOW TO REGISTER

Visit: <https://pediatricsweek.euroscicon.com/registration>

Call: 7025085200 ext: 8042

Email: europediatricsweek@speakertalk.org

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